

adsorbate. Most of the organic inhibitors are compounds with at least one polar functional groups having atoms of oxygen, sulphur, selenium and nitrogen.

In the present work pyridine derivatives have been studied. They have nitrogen as an electron donor atom. Hence nitrogen is regarded as the reactions centre for the establishment of the chemisorption process.

When copper plates is immersed in aqueous solution of potassium persulphate it gives Cu^{+2} ions according to the following reactions.

Acridine derivatives are widely used as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium and iron (II) in acidic media. Acridine and phenazine are found as excellent corrosion inhibitors for copper in 0.1M potassium persulphate solution. According to Kuznetsov^{1,2} and Iofa^{1,3} ions of nitrogen containing inhibitors are capable of being adsorbed predominantly on the most active regions of the dissolving metal. They reported that inhibition obtained by acridine is due to formation of protective layer on the metal surface.

It is qualitatively observed that these compounds give different types of coloured precipitates with copper ions in potassium persulphate solution.

Compounds	Colour of ppt,
Pyridine	Bright blue
Phenazine	Yellowish green crystalline
Acridine	Orange coloured crystalline
Xanthine	Slight white precipitate.

This is a strong evidence that most of the compounds have tendency to form complex compounds with copper ions. Due to the formation of insoluble complex compound, a thin adherent film is formed on the metal surface which prevents corrosion.

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Optically Active Unsymmetrical Ketones from S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-Bromobutane

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OPTICALLY active unsymmetrical aliphatic ketones¹ of the type, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}$ have been prepared by the Grignard reaction using optically active S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane and different alkyl cyanides. Treatment of 86% optically pure S-(+)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (I), $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$ dm), with bromine and red phosphorus resulted in S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (II), $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$ dm), which gave Grignard reagent (III). It was then reacted with different alkyl cyanides to obtain desired optically active ketones (IV). The alkyl cyanides are prepared from their respective alkyl bromides, while methyl, ethyl and *n*-propyl cyanides as they are water soluble were prepared from acetamide, propionamide and *n*-butyramide, respectively^{2,3}.

The bromine atom is away from the active center and not attached directly to the asymmetric carbon atom, therefore it is not disturbed during the reaction, hence the different alkyl substituted ketones were found to be optically active. The maximum rotation found in case of S-(+)-3-methyl-5-decanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 3.04$ ($l=1$ dm) and minimum rotation in case of S-(+)-3-methyl-5-tridecanone, $\alpha_D^{25} + 0.32$ ($l=1$ dm).

The physical properties including optical activity and infrared spectra are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol^{4,5}: The fusel oil contains one of the constituents as optically active S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol which was obtained by fractional distillation through 16 inch long column, b. p. $126^\circ - 128^\circ$. $\alpha_D^{25} - 4.62$ ($l=1$ dm); $d_4^{25} 0.8279$; $n_D^{25} 1.450$.

*S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane*⁶: It was prepared by bromination of S-(-)-2-methyl butan-1-ol (320 g.) with red phosphorus (20.7 g.) and liquid bromine (266.6 g., 86.1 ml.). The resulting S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane was obtained at $116^\circ - 118^\circ$. Yield 57.3%. $\alpha_D^{25} + 1.69$ ($l=1$ dm); $d_4^{25} 1.255$; $n_D^{25} 1.455$.

General method for the preparation of S-(+)-2-methyl-1-butyl n-alkyl ketone: To the Grignard reagent prepared from S-(+)-2-methyl-1-bromobutane (0.2 ml), dry magnesium (0.2 mole) and ether (100 ml), the alkyl cyanide (0.2 mole) in ether (40 ml) was added dropwise during 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 1 hr and kept overnight. On the next day the Grignard complex was decomposed by ammonium chloride solution (10%, 500 ml). The ketone was extracted with ether, washed with water, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled under reduced pressure.

TABLE 1—OPTICALLY ACTIVE UNSYMMETRICAL KETONES OF THE TYPE, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\overset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{C}}\text{H}\text{CH}_2\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}$

No.	Name	R	B.P. °C/15mm.	Yield %	S. Rotation $_{32}^{\infty}\text{D}$	d_4^{25}	n_D^{25}	Mol. formula	IR Spectra C=O Stretching vibrations
1.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-hexanone	Methyl	70-75	49.2	+1.44	0.9567	1.407	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$	1718 cm^{-1} (5.82 μ)
2.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-heptanone	Ethyl	80-90	36.2	+0.95	0.9672	1.413	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$	1721 cm^{-1} (5.81 μ)
3.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-octanone	n-Propyl	104-107	39.0	+0.59	0.9268	1.416	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$	1727 cm^{-1} (5.79 μ)
4.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-nonanone	n-Butyl	160-170	51.7	+1.10	0.9430	1.418	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$	1730 cm^{-1} (5.78 μ)
5.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-decanone	n-Amyl	135-137	53.6	+3.04	0.9651	1.412	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$	1727 cm^{-1} (5.79 μ)
6.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-undecanone	n-Hexyl	139-140	52.4	+1.05	0.9276	1.427	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$	1727 cm^{-1} (5.79 μ)
7.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-dodecanone	n-Heptyl	170-172 (25mm)	55.3	+0.57	0.9103	1.429	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}$	1721 cm^{-1} (5.81 μ)
8.	S-(+)-3-Methyl-5-tridecanone	n-octyl	108-110	53.4	+0.32	0.9095	1.439	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$	1730 cm^{-1} (5.78 μ)

All the compounds described gave correct C.H analysis.

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